

MAINTAINING THE ECOLOGICAL BALANCE IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS THROUGH NATURE PROTECTION AND ENJOYMENT, FROM NATURE REASONABLE USE.

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ANNOTATION: To preserve the ecological balance, rational use of nature in providing ecological education to the students by preserving and respecting nature. In this regard, the students were told that environmental education by protecting and respecting nature affects all areas of human life and that it is necessary to take immediate measures to prevent the negative consequences of climate change and adapt to new living conditions.

Key words: Technologies, nature conservation, Environment, nature, ecological scientists. trees, bushes, green areas.

INTRODUCTION: One of the most urgent issues of today's technology as a state-level problem is love for nature, its preservation is the protection of trees, bushes and green areas and the expansion of their areas, the more effective organization of the activities of responsible organizations in this area.

Also, in order to fulfill the tasks specified in the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 30, 2019 "On approval of the concept of environmental protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" No. PF-5863:

As we study the current problem of environmental education by forming the culture of environmental education by protecting and respecting nature, we will say that "Nature is an existence that exists even before the appearance of man and with the participation of man. A natural object is a substance, matter that exists in space and time" Nature is the first source that satisfies the material and spiritual needs of a person. For this reason, preservation and respect of nature is the most important issue that has been of interest to everyone until now. When we say nature, we mean the whole being, the universe, living and inanimate objects on our planet. Humans, plants, animals and microorganisms belong to the living part of the earth, and air, water and rock layers belong to the non-living part. They are inextricably linked.

Nature is a cradle for man, a mother's embrace. His bosom is wide, and his heart is always open for people. He does not spare his generosity and treats

from people. And the land is the source of total wealth and blessings. That is why it is honored and glorified by humanity and recognized as mother earth.

Today, we often hear concepts such as "climate changes", "global warming", "ecological stress", "ecological threat", "ecological disaster", "ecological crisis" in our living conditions and providing environmental education by protecting and respecting nature. We are witnessing, and it is showing its negative effects on a person. Today, climate change is recognized by the world community as the most serious problem facing humanity. In this regard, in providing environmental education to students by protecting and respecting nature, climate change affects all areas of human life and emphasizes the need to take immediate measures to prevent the negative consequences of climate change and adapt to new living conditions. The environmental scientists of the world and modern science provide serious reasons confirming that the negative consequences of climate change have a significant impact on humanity and its gene pool and life. In this regard, in the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev at the 72nd session of the United Nations, the problems of our nation, as well as the world, the problems of the Island, its ecological tragedy and the issues of its prevention were raised. After that, that is, at the same time, preservation and respect of nature has become one of the issues in the world's attention as the most urgent problem of the whole world. It is noteworthy that in Article 49 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Everyone has the right to a comfortable environment and reliable information about its condition." The state creates conditions for the implementation of public control in the field of urban planning activities in order to ensure the environmental rights of citizens and prevent harmful effects on the environment. Drafts of urban planning documents are subject to public discussion in accordance with the law. In accordance with the principle of sustainable development, the state implements measures to improve, restore and protect the environment, maintain ecological balance. It is also very important to state that the state will take measures to protect and restore the ecological system of the Aral Bay region, and to develop the region socially and economically. In his speech at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan **Shavkat Mirziyoyev** emphasized the need to actively unite the world community, including the countries of the region, in environmental issues, including international efforts to eliminate the consequences of the drying up of the Aral Sea. Today, we are all witnesses of practical work in these matters. As just one example, the establishment of the

multi-partner "Trust" fund for human security under the auspices of the UN, or during the first year of independence, 400,000 hectares of forest was established in the dry bottom of the island, and in the last three years it can be mentioned that seeds of saxovol and main desert plants were sown and seedlings were planted on nearly 1500 thousand hectares. Also, in this area, the decision of our President "On approving the strategy of transition to the economy on the basis of the national project "Green Space" of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period of 2019-2030" and a number of points of the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan on preservation and respect of nature, environmental protection and ecological condition the determination of the issues of increasing attention to improvement serves as a direct legal basis for climate change prevention and adaptation. According to the analysis and opinion of experts, in 2030-2050, the air temperature in the region may increase by 1.5-3°C. It is expected that the air temperature will rise, especially in the Aral Bay, which may cause problems related to local climate changes.

CONCLUSION: Today's reforms in the field of education in the newly developing Republic of Uzbekistan are changing the practical forms, methods and tools of environmental education technologies to students by preserving and respecting nature in accordance with the requirements of the time. The relevance of the problems of environmental education and protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the protection and preservation of nature to students is recognized as an important task for the science of pedagogy and schools. This raises the issue of educating the young generation who knows how to maintain ecological balance and use natural resources wisely, to provide ecological education to students by protecting and respecting nature.

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